

VHDL-Based Implementations of Area and Power Efficient Filter Architectures

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ABSTRACT

Digital signal processing operations, e.g., digital filters, are one important class of application in communication devices. A digital filtering algorithm can be implemented in various ways by selecting one architecture from the set of possible realizations. By choosing an advanced architecture notable advantages in both the silicon area and power dissipation can be achieved compared to the conventional direct-form realization. This paper focuses on interpolated finite impulse response (interpolated FIR) filter and recursive running-sum (RRS) filter based architectures. The VHDL-based implementations prove that these advanced architectures are efficient when low-power or low-area characteristics are desired. Over 55 percent savings in the area and in the power dissipation were achieved when an FIR filter with a narrow transition band was implemented using these architectures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Linear-phase FIR filters are widely used in communication devices due to their many attractive properties. For these filters, the number of multipliers required in the implementation is approximately half the filter order when exploiting the coefficient symmetry. The order can be estimated in the lowpass case by [1]

$$N = \frac{-20 \log \sqrt{\delta_p \delta_s} - 13}{14.6(\omega_s - \omega_p)/(2\pi)} \quad (1)$$

where δ_p and δ_s are the passband and stopband ripples, whereas ω_p and ω_s are the band edges in terms of the angular frequency. As seen from the above equation, the filter order as well as the number of multipliers is roughly inversely proportional to the transition bandwidth. This means that a high number of multipliers are needed for implementing filters with a narrow transition bandwidth. By using advanced filter structures, the number of arithmetic operations – especially multipliers – can be significantly reduced.

Two advanced FIR filter architectures are studied in this paper. These architectures are more complex than

a direct-form realization in the sense that the order of the filter is higher. However, this drawback is compensated because the overall amount of needed hardware is smaller. Both architectures were implemented using VHDL. Next, the power consumption and the required silicon area were estimated. Finally, the estimates were compared to the direct-form conventional FIR realizations.

2 POWER CONSUMPTION IN INTEGRATED CIRCUITS

Low power consumption means cheaper packaging and cooling costs, more reliable circuits, and in portable products longer operating times. The area of silicon in integrated circuits (ICs) has a direct effect on the manufacturing costs. Thus, the power consumption and the area are two very important design constraints. They can be controlled in all the levels of the design process. However, the higher is the used abstraction level, the better are the results. That is the reason why the realization structure should be selected in the higher abstraction levels – for example in the architectural level [2]-[4].

The power consumption is not constant in time. Especially in portable products, the average consumption is the most important optimization metric, because it has a direct effect on the lifetime of batteries. The average power consumption consists of four factors

$$P_{avg} = P_{dynamic} + P_{short-circuit} + P_{leakage} + P_{static}. \quad (2)$$

In CMOS circuits, the dynamic power consumption is usually the most significant factor. It can be defined as

$$P_{dynamic} = KC_{out}V_{dd}^2f, \quad (3)$$

where C_{out} is the output capacitance, V_{dd} the supply voltage and f the clock frequency of the circuit. K is the average number of transitions of the output node in a clock cycle divided by two [5].

Figure 1: Implementation for $F(z^L)$ exploiting the coefficient symmetry.

3 INTERPOLATED FIR ARCHITECTURE

For interpolated FIR filters [6]–[9], the transfer function is constructed as a cascade of two terms as follows:

$$H(z) = A(z)G(z) = F(z^L)G(z). \quad (4)$$

Here, the first term $A(z) = F(z^L)$ is obtained from the conventional transfer function $F(z)$ by replacing each unit delay with L unit delays, that is, a block of L delays.

In the time domain, this means that if the order of $F(z)$ is N_F and the impulse response coefficients are $f(n)$ for $n = 0, 1, \dots, N_F$, then the order of $A(z)$ is LN_F . Furthermore, the impulse-response coefficients of $A(z)$, $a(n)$ for $n = 0, 1, \dots, LN_F$, are obtained by inserting $L - 1$ zero-valued samples between the original samples of $f(n)$, that is,

$$a(n) = \begin{cases} f(n/L) & \text{for } m = 0, L, \dots, LN_F \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1 shows an implementation for $F(z^L)$ exploiting the coefficient symmetry.

The attractive property in generating $A(z) = F(z^L)$ in the above manner lies in the fact that the amplitude response of $A(z) = F(z^L)$ is a frequency-axis compressed version of that of $F(z)$ such that the interval $[0, L\pi]$ is shrunk onto $[0, \pi]$. This is illustrated in Fig. 2 for $L = 5$. There are the following two consequences. First, if the passband and stopband edges for $F(z)$ are θ and ϕ , then the corresponding edges for $A(z) = F(z^L)$ are $\omega_p = \theta/L$ and $\omega_s = \phi/L$. Second, the periodicity of $A(z) = F(z^L)$ is $2\pi/L$ so that there are extra unwanted passband and transition band regions in the baseband region $[0, \pi]$.

The first consequence is the desired one. $A(z) = F(z^L)$ of order LN_F provides the transition from the passband edge located at $\omega_p = \theta/L$ to the stopband edge located at $\omega_s = \phi/L$ with only $N_F + 1$ non-zero impulse-response coefficients. Since the filter order is roughly inversely proportional to the transition bandwidth, the order of the corresponding direct-form FIR filter is approximately equal to LN_F , requiring $LN_F + 1$

Figure 2: A frequency response of a periodic FIR filter $F(z^L)$ for $L = 5$.

non-zero coefficients. Hence, $A(z) = F(z^L)$ provides the same transition bandwidth with approximately the same filter order, but the number of multipliers is only $(1/L)$ th of that of the direct-form filter.

As shown in Fig. 2, $A(z) = F(z^L)$ cannot be directly used as a lowpass filter due to the unwanted passband and transition band regions. Therefore, the overall transfer function $H(z)$, as given by Eq. (4), is a cascade of $A(z) = F(z^L)$ and $G(z)$. The role of $G(z)$ is to attenuate the unwanted extra passband and transition band regions.

In practice, ω_p and ω_s as well as the passband and stopband ripples for the amplitude response of the overall transfer $H(z)$ are specified. The problem is then to select L in such a way that the given criteria are met with the minimum number of multipliers. This problem has been considered in details in [7]–[9]. The best results can be achieved by designing $F(z^L)$ and $G(z)$ simultaneously in such a way that $G(z)$ has all of its zeros on the unit circle and attenuates the extra unwanted passband and transition band regions, whereas $F(z^L)$ takes care of the overall response in the interval $[0, \pi/L]$.

4 RECURSIVE RUNNING-SUM FIR ARCHITECTURE

Further savings in the implementation costs can be achieved if a more sophisticated architecture is selected. One resource efficient implementation is based on a transfer function

$$G(z) = \prod_{r=1}^{M_p} T_r(z), \quad (6)$$

where

$$T_r(z) = 2^{-P_r} \sum_{k=0}^{K_r-1} z^{-k} = 2^{-P_r} \frac{1 - z^{-K_r}}{1 - z^{-1}} \quad (7)$$

2^{-P_r} is a scaling constant and $K_r - 1$ is the number of zeros on the unit circle [8], [10]. This RRS architecture, which is shown in Fig. 3, is multiplier-free.

Figure 3: A recursive running-sum implementation of $T_r(z)$.

Table 1: The implementation parameters for Case 1.

Filter order	108
Interface precision	16 bits
Internal precision	16/32 bits
Coefficient precision	16 bits
Number of delays	108
Number of multipliers	58

5 VHDL-BASED IMPLEMENTATIONS

The used test case is the implementation of a linear-phase FIR filter with the specifications: $\omega_p = 0.05\pi$, $\omega_s = 0.1\pi$, $\delta_p = 0.01$, and $\delta_s = 0.001$ (60-dB stop-band attenuation). For comparison purposes, we use the designs given in [8]. For the direct-form FIR filter, a 109-tap FIR filter (order is 108) is required to meet the given criteria. This design is here referred to as Case 1. For Case 2, the overall filter is implemented as a cascade of $F(z^L)$ and a conventional direct-form $G(z)$ (cf. Eq. (4)), whereas for Case 3, $G(z)$ is a cascade of four RRS filters.

The implementation properties of Case 1 and Case 2 can be found from Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. Table 3 shows the parameters of $F(z^L)$ in Case 3. The properties of the RRS-filter $G(z)$ are presented in Table 4. The precision of the filters was selected in such a way that the filters fulfil their frequency-domain requirements in the gate-level simulations.

The test architectures were synthesized to the gate level using a $0.35 \mu\text{m}$ technology, which has a supply voltage of 2 volts. The gate level simulation took place after synthesis. The switching activity values were gath-

Table 2: The implementation parameters for Case 2.

	Interpolated FIR	FIR
Filter order	17	17
L	6	1
Interface precision	16 bits	18 bits
Internal precision	32 bits	34 bits
Coefficient precision	16 bits	16 bits
Number of delays	102	17
Number of multipliers	18	18

Table 3: The implementation parameters of $F(z^L)$ in Case 3.

Filter order	10
L	8
Interface precision	18 bits
Internal precision	34 bits
Coefficient precision	16 bits
Number of delays	80
Number of multipliers	11

Table 4: The implementation parameters of $G(z)$ in Case 3.

T	4
$K_{r,s}$	17, 15, 12, 10
$P_{r,s}$	6, 4, 3, 3
Interface precision	18 bits
Internal precision	32 bits

ered during this simulation by tracking the activity in the internal nodes of the circuits with the VSS tool (from Synopsys Inc.). Using the switching activity values, the average power consumption was studied. DesignPower tool (from Synopsys Inc.) was used for the power analysis. Also the area and the maximum combinatorial delay of the implementations were evaluated. In the simulations two different input data were used. One was a binary dump from a music tune (November Rain from Metallica) and another was randomly distributed noise, which was generated using Matlab (from the Math Works, Inc.). From now on these data patterns are called the music and noise, respectively. The values in the music are always positive. This means that there are no sign changes. In theory, this data is less power consuming than the noise, because 2's complement number system is used. The relative area and the longest combinatorial delay of the architectures is presented in Table 5.

The power consumption with the music as input data is illustrated Fig. 4 (1: Case 1, 2: Case 2, 3: Case

Table 5: The relative area and the delay of the filter systems.

Case	Architecture	Relative area	Delay (ns)
1	Conventional transposed FIR	1.00	21.4
2	Interpolated FIR with conventional $G(z)$	0.62	21.6
3	Interpolated FIR with RRS-based $G(z)$	0.47	23.9

Figure 4: The power consumption for the three FIR filter design cases. (20 MHz sampling rate, music input)

Figure 5: The power consumption for the three FIR filter design cases. (20 MHz sampling rate, noise input).

3). The power consumption with the noise input is presented in Fig. 5.

6 CONCLUSION

Two advanced FIR filter architectures, interpolated FIR filter with a conventional FIR subfilter and a RRS subfilter, were implemented using VHDL and logic synthesis. The results of the evaluation indicate that the interpolated FIR-RRS structure is the most promising for low-power applications. That structure consumed 55% less power than a conventional filter structure — still fulfilling the given filter requirements. By using lower level

power and area optimization methods together with architectural solutions, even more power savings can be achieved.

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